

THE HYDROLYTIC CONSTANT AND HEAT OF HYDROLYSIS OF HYDROXYLAMINE HYDROCHLORIDE

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The hydrolytic constant of hydroxylamine has been determined from conductance and p_H measurements. The heat of hydrolysis derived has been confirmed by solubility and calorimetric experiments.

The hydrolysis of hydroxylamine hydrochloride was first measured by Winkelblech (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1901, 36, 574) and then by Veley (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1908, 93, 659). Arneölander (*Z. physikal. Chem.*, 1927, 129, 1) determined the dissociation constant of hydroxylamine by a colorimetric method. Isikawa and Aoki (*Bull. Inst. Phys. Chem. Res.*, Tokyo, 1940, 19, 136) and Hagsawa, *ibid.*, 1941, 20, 251) derived the hydrolytic and dissociation constants from p_H measurements with the glass electrode. But whilst Winkelblech's data implied a K_h value of 6.26×10^{-7} at 25° , Hagsawa's was 10.40×10^{-7} . In view of the discrepancy in the K_h values derived by the above workers, the present study was undertaken, using conductance measurements at different dilutions and temperatures. p_H determinations were made to verify the hydrolytic constant obtained at 30° . Further experiments were carried out to check the heat of hydrolysis from solubility and calorimetric determinations.

EXPERIMENTAL

In the conductance measurements Philips A.F. oscillator G. M. 2307 was used as the source of A. C. The present experiments were conducted on a frequency of 1 kc./s. A platinum-iridium slide wire of a meter length, a resistance box, a sensitive headphone and Philips' dip type conductivity cell were the other parts of the equipment. Tower's thermostatic unit was used to maintain a constant temperature of the bath. The p_H determinations were carried out with Beckman's p_H -meter, model G.

In the solubility measurements were used tightly stoppered bottles which could be shaken in a bath maintained at the desired temperature. Thermochemical data were obtained with a Cenco vacuum-jacketed calorimeter, using a calibrated Beckmann thermometer.

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride was of B.D.H. Analar quality and gave no test for ammonia. Hydroxylamine was prepared by Hurd and Brownstein's method (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 47, 67). All other chemicals were of Analar grade. Hydroxylamine was estimated iodimetrically as done by Arneölander (*loc. cit.*). Preliminary experiments showed this method as good as the bromate method.

Conductance Data.—After determining the cell constant, the conductivity of hydrochloric acid and of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in aqueous solution and in solution containing added hydroxylamine, were measured. All solutions had the same normality.

According to Ross (Mellor, "Comprehensive Treatise in Inorganic and Theoretical Chemistry", Vol. VIII, p. 284) the conductivity of hydroxylamine salt solutions increases with time due to decomposition of salt on the platinum black electrodes. In order to minimise this, the dip electrodes and salt solutions were kept in the thermostat in separate vessels and the electrodes were dipped in the salt only at the time of taking the resistance reading. The degree of hydrolysis (x) and the hydrolytic constant, K_h , were computed from the usual relations :

$$x = \frac{\text{Conductance of hydrolysed salt—cond. of unhydrolysed salt}}{\text{Conductance of HCl—cond. of unhydrolysed salt}}$$

$$\text{and } K_h = \frac{x^2}{(1-x) V}$$

where all conductances were measured at the dilution V litres per g. equivalent. The data thus obtained at two temperature are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Conc.	Hydrolysed salt.	Unhydrolysed salt.	HCl.	100x.	$K_h \times 10^7$.
Conductance at 30°.					
<i>N</i> /100	109.74	106.90	451.22	0.83	6.95
<i>N</i> /1000	153.24	145.22	462.54	2.53	6.57
<i>N</i> /5000	171.19	154.12	464.32	5.50	6.40
<i>N</i> /10000	179.40	154.82	465.46	7.91	6.78
					Mean 6.68
Conductance at 20°.					
<i>N</i> /100	108.17	105.82	372.32	0.88	7.81
<i>N</i> /1000	150.12	143.73	377.54	2.73	7.66
<i>N</i> /5000	165.98	152.44	380.33	5.94	7.50
<i>N</i> /10000	174.16	155.25	382.05	8.34	7.59
					Mean 7.64

The p_H measurements were taken at the room temperature ($30^\circ \pm 0.5^\circ$), the relationship used being :

$$PK_h = 2 p_H - P_c$$

where P terms are negative logarithms of the respective quantities. Table II contains these data.

TABLE II

Conc.	p_H	PK_h	$K_h \times 10^7$.
<i>N</i> /100	4.03	6.16	6.92
<i>N</i> /1000	4.59	6.18	6.61
<i>N</i> /5000	4.94	6.18	6.61
<i>N</i> /10000	5.08	6.16	6.92
			Mean 6.77

The values of the hydrolytic constants from conductivity and p_H determinations at 30° are in good agreement. A comparison of the hydrolytic constants at 30° and 20° shows that hydrolysis of hydroxylamine hydrochloride is an exothermic process. Use of Vant Hoff's isochore yields 2.37 k cal. as the heat of hydrolysis.

In the solubility measurements, a saturated solution of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in distilled water and in *N*-HCl was prepared at 15° to 40°, and this was analysed iodimetrically. As hydrolysis is repressed in the presence of HCl, the observations here show the heat of solution of hydroxylamine; but the data obtained in aqueous solution comprise heat of solution and heat of hydrolysis. Table III records the results of solubility experiments.

TABLE III

Temp. ...	15°	20°	25°	30°	35°	40°
Moles of salt/litre solution in						
(a) water ...	18.32	19.49	20.65	21.90	22.99	24.48
(b) aq. HCl...	15.85	17.99	20.20	22.98	25.52	28.20

Plots of log solubility against $1/T^{\circ}$ (absolute) yield the following values of heat changes involved: (a) -2.17; (b) -4.13 k cal. From these the heat of solution -4.13 k cal. and the heat of hydrolysis + 1.96 k cal. may be derived.

In the calorimetric measurements, the water equivalent was obtained from observations on the heat of solution of potassium chloride, taking this to be 4200 cal./mol. (Barieaue and Giaque, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 5676). A thin glass bulb containing a weighed amount of salt was sealed off and dropped into the calorimeter vessel containing a known weight of distilled water or normal hydrochloric acid. The bulb was broken by pressing with the stirrer. Temperature was read on a calibrated Beckmann thermometer. Corrections were made for the heat capacity of thermometer bulb, stirrer and broken tube. The data are recorded in Table IV.

TABLE IV

Water equiv. of calorimeter = 11.80 cal.

Heat capacity of stirrer, thermometer bulb and broken glass = 1.14 cal.

(a) Weight of water taken = 99.5 g.

(b) Weight of HCl solution = 101.99 g.
Sp. heat of „ 0.96 cal.

Salt taken.	Fall in temp.	Heat change (k cal./mol.)	Salt taken.	Fall in temp.	Heat change (k cal./mol.)
1. $8.35 \times 10^{-3}M$	0.13°	-1.750	1. $11.56 \times 10^{-3}M$	0.41	-3.930
2. 11.59	0.19°	-1.844	2. 9.59	0.35	-4.044
3. 13.03	0.21°	-1.812	3. 7.00	0.25	-3.958
		Mean -1.80			Mean -3.98

From Table V, the value of heat of solution is -3.98 k cal. and heat of hydrolysis is + 2.18 k cal.

The heat of solution obtained from solubility and calorimetry are within 1 k cal. of the values given in Rossini's Thermochemistry of Chemical Substances (Reinhold, p. 216):

Berthelot: -3.35; Thomsen: -3.65; present authors: -4.13 and -3.98 k cal.

The heat of hydrolysis could not be found in literature; the values derived in this work from three different methods are in close agreement: conductance + 2.37; solubility + 1.96; calorimetry + 2.18 k cal.

Besides, the hydrolytic constant, measured conductometrically at 30°, implies a value of 2.202×10^{-3} for the basic dissociation constant of hydroxylamine which agrees with the value obtained spectrophotometrically (reported in the next paper).

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